

Popular Article

Rabbit as an alternative source of meat and wool production

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Abstract

Rabbits are being reared in our country for a long time. The first record in the history of human's relationship with the rabbit was documented in early Roman times. 'Cuniculture' is the agricultural practice of breeding and raising domestic rabbits as livestock for their meat, fur or wool, cuniculture has been practiced since at least from 5th century. China has emerged as the lead country and has emerged as a major producer of rabbit meat, fur and angora wool in the world. Rabbit is regarded as one of the most useful among 'micro livestock' as considered by FAO and other organization. Rabbit rearing is popular for meat, fur, skin and wool production. Rabbit meat is wholesome; tasty which is rich in protein, certain minerals and vitamins but low in fat and cholesterol. In India North Eastern Hill region is one of the highest meat consuming zones, considering high demand of meat and meat products, farming of rabbit in this region has more scope as an alternative source of meat.

Introduction

Domestic/modern rabbit belongs to genus *Oryctolagus* (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*). Rabbit meat has great potential in meeting worlds need in general and developing countries in particular. The increasingly important role of rabbit, breeding/farming and its potential to improve food security and nutrition in developing countries has been increased by the FAO, because it is a low-cost proposition, the meat is nutritious and there is less social, cultural, and religious restriction against it. Broiler rabbits are reared for meat and fur and Angora rabbits for wool production.

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Breeds of Rabbit

There are 38 breeds of domestic rabbits recognized throughout the world, but only 8-10 breeds are available in India. For Indian weather White Giant, Grey Giant, Flemish Giant (largest domestic breed), New Zealand White (Best meat breed), New Zealand Red, California, Soviet and Dutch Chinchilla breeds are suitable.

House of Rabbit

Selection of site for construction of shed should be preferred as elevated area having easy drainage system and well protected from predators (dog, fox and cat) of rabbit. For rearing of rabbit generally deep litter and battery/cage systems are applied. To get maximum production, housing cost must be low, well ventilated, ideal temperature (10⁰-25⁰c) and knowledge on floor allowance is very important. Floor space requirement is depending according to different body weight of rabbits-up to 2 kg-0.04 m², 2-4 kg-0.28 m², 4-5 kg-0.37 m² and over 5.5 kg-0.46 m² floor space is required.

Benefits of Rabbit farming

There are many advantages of commercial farming in India. Bunnies are cute, small sized and soft therefore are a good source of meat.

- The initial investment cost for rabbit farming is low and gave quick return, just after 6 months of establishment of the farm. Small groups 40-50 in numbers can rear in the backyard of the house with kitchen waste and some grasses as feed.
- Rabbits are highly prolific, and give birth of 25-50 young ones (Kits) per year. The gestation periods of rabbits are 28-32 (average 30 days) days and selling age of rabbit is 90-100 days.
- Rabbit meat is widely popular meat throughout many different cultures of the world. Rabbit meat is rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA) and comes under category of white meat,

which is exceptionally lean, lower calories, lower fat, and higher protein and very palatable excellent quality. Rabbit meats can be processed at the age of around 12 weeks.

- Rabbits are best producer of wool (require 30% less digestible energy to produce 1 kg of wool as compared to sheep). Angora rabbit is used for production of one of the finest wools in the world. Rabbit's wool is 6-8 times warmer than contemporary sheep wool.
- They also provide good source of income from sale of Pelt, Kits, and manure other than meat. Rabbit skins are used for making fur garments, hats, and hand gloves etc.
- The use of Rabbits in biomedical research as animals is extensive now-a-days. Rabbit blood is one of the best medium for growing the AIDS virus.
- Rabbit manure used as organic manure, it is richer in Nitrogen, Phosphorous, Potassium which are remaining in proportion of (3.7: 1.3: 3.5) as compared to the cattle manure (2.9: 0.7: 2.1)

Conclusion

Rabbits are highly prolific, low body size, rapid growth rate, short gestation period, early maturity, high genetic potential, efficient feed and land utilization, ability to utilize forage and fibrous agricultural byproducts. Therefore, it is considered that if scientific management and hygienic practices of rabbit farming are followed it can be established as a highly profitable business. In India, there has been a rising awareness in recent years as a broiler rabbit production act as an alternative means of alleviating food shortage.

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